

Studies on the Formation of Complex Compounds of Mercuric Chloride with Amines and Phenols

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Formation of the compounds of mercuric chloride with phenols and amines in anhydrous ethanol has been studied viscometrically. The viscosity-composition curves show the formation of compounds, some of which have also been isolated and analysed.

Nayar and Srivastava¹ studied viscosities of HgCl_2 and KCl systems in water and observed six breaks in viscosity-concentration curves, which they attributed to the formation of complex compounds. Yajnik and Roy² studied the complex formation of HgCl_2 with other univalent chlorides as well as with HCl viscometrically and concluded the formation of bivalent HgCl_4^{2-} .

A very few complex compounds of mercuric chloride with phenols and amines are reported in the literature. The present investigation has been undertaken with a view to studying the formation of complex compounds of HgCl_2 with amines and phenols in ethanolic medium viscometrically and to isolating them, if possible.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of B. D. H. 'extra pure' quality. Ethanol was dehydrated and redistilled. Equimolecular solutions of mercuric chloride, phenols, amines, etc. were prepared in anhydrous ethanol.

In all the cases monovariant system was followed, *i.e.* the volume of one of the components was kept constant (10 ml) and the volume of the other gradually changed (5, 10, 15, 20 ml etc.), the total volume being made to 50 ml by addition of anhydrous ethanol in each case. The viscosity of each mixture was determined at a constant temperature by Ostwald's viscometer, kept in a thermostat (Townson and Mercer Ltd.), and plotted against the volume of the phenol solution (Fig. 1-3).

The mixture of the solutions, corresponding to the peak observed in the graph, was concentrated and the compound crystallised in a vacuum desiccator. It was dried over fused CaCl_2 in a vacuum desiccator and analysed. The results are recorded in Table I. In the case of diphenylamine, *o*-, and *p*-nitroanilines, the compounds were also prepared by adding an excess of the organic substance to HgCl_2 solution, but the compounds obtained were the same as those obtained with the calculated quantities.

1. *This Journal*, 1952, 29, 241.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 902.

Mercury was estimated as HgS and chlorine as AgCl by Piria and Schiff's method. Nitrogen was estimated in a few cases and the percentage of organic matter calculated. In the rest, it was found by difference.

TABLE I

Organic compounds.	Viscosity-molar ratio. (HgCl ₂ : org. comp.).	Colour.	M.P.	Found.	Calc.	Probable formula.
1 2,4-Dinitro-naphthol	1:1	Dirty yellow	**125°	Hg : 41.40% Cl : 15.10 +OM : 43.50	33.60% 14.10 46.30	HgCl ₂ (NO ₂) ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₅ OH
2 o-Aminophenol	1:1	own	**240°	Hg : 41.69 Cl : 14.89 N : 5.64 OM : 43.90	40.90 14.50 5.72 44.50	HgCl ₂ .2NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ OH
3 o-Aminophenol*	1:1	..	**238°	Hg : 40.10 Cl : 13.98 N : 5.32 OM : 43.30	40.90 14.50 5.72 44.50	HgCl ₂ .2NH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ OH
4 o-Nitrophenol	1:1	Green	**180°	Hg : 35.20 Cl : 13.42 OM : 51.38	36.40 12.90 50.60	HgCl ₂ .2NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ OH
5 Diphenylamine	1:2	Black	**65°	Hg : 31.64 Cl : 11.02 N : 4.48 OM : 53.86	33.10 11.60 4.59 55.40	HgCl ₂ .2(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ NH
6 o-Nitroaniline	1:1	Orange	115°	Hg : 49.42 Cl : 16.83 OM : 34.75	48.80 17.30 33.80	HgCl ₂ .NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂
7 p-Nitroanisole	1:1	Yellowish white	**168°	Hg : 34.70 Cl : 12.30 OM : 53.00	35.02 12.40 53.50	HgCl ₂ .2NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃

*In ethyl acetate medium.

**Denotes decomposition temperature.

† OM denotes organic matter.

General Properties.—Almost all the compounds are coloured, semicrystalline powder, insoluble in benzene and CCl₄, but soluble in ethanol, ethyl acetate, and acetone. The compound formed with diphenylamine is sparingly soluble in organic solvents. The compounds do not melt sharply, but decompose when heated. The compounds are fairly stable at the room temperature.

DISCUSSION

From the viscosity-composition curves (Fig. 1-3) it is evident that a distinct peak is obtained in each case, which indicates the formation of complex compounds. With phenols, substituted phenols, acetophenone, benzophenone, and diphenylamine, it is observed at the molar ratio of HgCl₂ to the other compounds as 1:2, showing thereby that only -OH

Organic compounds (ml)

FIG. 1

Temp. = 30°.

0.1N-HgCl₂ = 10ml.

Medium = EtOH.

Organic compounds (ml).

FIG. 2

Conditions same as in Fig. 1

FIG. 3

groups in phenols and substituted phenols, -NH group in diphenylamine, -CO group in benzophenone and acetophenone are co-ordinating. With amino- and nitro-phenol, it is observed at 1:1 which shows that both the -OH and -NH₂ groups in the former and -OH and -NO₂ groups in the later are co-ordinating.

Though in the case of amino- and nitro-phenols the peak is observed at the molar ratio of HgCl₂ to the phenol as 1:1, the compounds isolated are in 1:2 ratio. It appears that -OH being a weak co-ordinating group, its reaction is inhibited by strong -NH₂ and -NO₂ groups.

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